
JAMMU AND KASHMIR ASSEMBLY ELECTIONS: POLITICAL PROCESSES AND PEOPLES ASPIRATIONS

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Abstract

The objective of this study is to highlight the processes of Jammu and Kashmir (J&K) assembly elections and to explore the expectations of people regarding these elections. The assembly elections in J&K were held on a regular basis from 1951 when Constituent Assembly of J&K was framed. The people, as well as the communal parties of J&K, actively participated in these elections till the 1990s like the other states of the country. They raised their problems through democratic ways and wanted solutions through these ways. They also expected the solution of J&K problem through Democratic ways. The rigidness of these elections process by incumbent parties and by the Central government not only kept away them from participating in these elections but they also lost faith in the democratic processes. From the 1990s the insurgency started in J&K. The people, as well as communal parties, actively supported it which also resulted in the decrease in people's participation in elections of J&K. Subsequently, from 2002 the elections were considered free and fair by almost all parties, but it could not bring back the communal parties into contesting elections. Nowadays the participation of people gradually increased in assembly elections of the state which is really a good sign for the democratic process in J&K. The study will try to unfold the reasons behind these developments in democratic processes in the state of J&K.

Key Words: Jammu and Kashmir, Assembly Elections, Democratic Process, Political Processes.

Introduction

In J&K the democratic processes started with the elections of Constituent Assembly in 1951. The constituent assembly was given the task of framing the constitution of the state. The assembly elections there after held on regular basis till 1990s. During 1990s the armed militancy started in the state which affects almost every sphere of life and also hurdles in conducting the assembly elections on regular basis in J&K. Presently not only the assembly elections were held on regular basis but also the participation of people also increased in these elections. Apart from this these elections were now considered free and fair by almost all political parties.

Results and Discussion

The state of J&K had few political parties when it accessed with Indian Union. This hurdles in participation of people in democratic processes. It also resulted in unopposition contest in assembly elections of J&K. In 1951 assembly election National Conference (NC) won all 75 seats in 73 were unopposed. Praja Parshid were filed 29 nomination papers, 16 were rejected and the remaining 13 withdrew their papers. Harijan Mandal were contested on two seats but withdrew blank.

In 1957 legislative elections NC, Praja Parshid, Harijan Mandal, Praja Socialist Party and Independents were in fray. NC won 68 seats (41) unopposed, Praja Parshid five seats, Harijan Mandal

and Independents one seat each. The president of Praja Parshid, Prem Nath Dogra, charged that ruling party had rigged the elections and manipulated the situation to get the majority in the assembly. The elections were held under the control of the state Election and Franchise Commissioner (Bhushan, 2008, 529-530).

Elections of 1962 were first time held under the auspices of the Election Commission of India (Singh, 1982, 162). NC won 70 seats (34) unopposed, Praja Parshid three seats and Independents two seats. Out of 294 nomination papers filed, 57 were rejected mostly on unjustified grounds. Sixty three candidates were forced to withdraw from contest under intimidation. The opposition parties once again charged the ruling NC indulging in unfair practices. Out of 13 candidates put up in 11 constituencies in the valley, five decided to retire as they had lost all hopes of fair elections (Qureshi, 1982, 54).

After the formation of congress, the units of Communist Party of India (Marxist) (CPIM) and Communist Party of India (CPI) were also formed. In 1967 legislative assembly four national Parties namely the Congress, the PSP, Jana Sangh, the CPI and three regional parties namely the NC, Plebiscite Front and the Democratic National Conference (DNC) in addition to independents were in the fray.

The Indian National Congress won 61 seats (22 unopposed) and got 53.36 percent of the popular votes. Jana Sangh could win only three seats and the NC led by G. M. Bakshi got eight seats. The three parties CPI, D.N.C. and Plebiscite Front virtually drew a blank. This time the trend of unopposed slightly dropped from 32 to 22.

The fifth general Assembly elections were held in 1972. Out of 612 nominations filed only 329 candidates contested. Moreover, in addition to All India parties, several other local parties like Jamat-i-Islamic and the Awami-Action Committee came up. This time only five uncontested seats returned to Assembly. The Congress Party won 58 seats, suffered loss of three Srinagar Constituencies. Jana Sangh won all three seats from Jammu region. The first time contestant Jamat-i-Islami was able to get only five seats. The four parties Congress (O), Swtantra Party, Socialist Party and CPI drew blank in this election (Bhushan, 2008, 531-532).

The prolonged battle for “self-determination” soon came to an end in 1974. The Sheikh and his associates reached an agreement with Mrs. Gandhi’s Government in 1974 and decided to “cast away their pro-plebiscite robe and don the pro-accession attire”. Actually, it had put another “seal of people’s approval on state’s accession to India” (Verma, 1994, 56-57). The self-determination virtually came to an end with the 1975 accord.

The Accord was followed by Sheikh assuming charge as the Chief Minister on 25 February, 1975. Mr. Mir Qasim, who headed the congress government, stepped down in favour of Sheikh Abdullah. After assuming power, the Sheikh dissolved the ‘Plebiscite Front’ on 05 July, 1975 and merged with the newly revived NC.

The sixth assembly election of 1977 was held under governor’s rule for the first time. The seats of State Assembly increased from 75 to 76 under Twelfth Amendment of 1975. Out of 754 nomination papers filed, 366 were from 44 constituencies of Kashmir division and 388 for 32 constituencies of Jammu division. However, the nomination papers of 13 candidates were rejected.

The NC won 47 seats, 40 from Kashmir Valley and seven from Jammu division. The Janata Party secured 13 seats, two from Kashmir valley and 11 from Jammu province. Meanwhile the Congress secured 11 seats-one from the Kashmir valley and 10 from the Jammu region. The independents won one seat that too from Jammu division. These elections were said to be free and fair. These elections did witness some violence but not to a point of making poll impossible. The most significant event was the total absence of the unopposed candidates (Bhushan, 2008, 532-533).

The seventh assembly election was unique as it was for the first time that NC was contesting elections in the absence of Sheikh Mohammad Abdullah. The Congress (I) election strategy was to win the maximum number of seats from Jammu region and then some of the strongholds of NC in the Kashmir valley (Bhushan, 2008, 533).

The data shows that NC won 26 seats in the election. The NC got overwhelming majority in the valley and improved its position in Jammu division including in Hindu majority district of Jammu which was once a stronghold of BJP. The Congress won 26 seats from the Jammu region. The people rejected other parties as is reflected in the results. The Panthers Party and Peoples Conference won one seat each and Independents got two seats. The other parties, BJP, Janta Party, Lok dal, Jamat-i-islami, CPI and CPI (M) drew blank.

Soon after the elections, Congress (I) demanded the dismissal of Farooq's government, for its failure to maintain law and order in the state. The confrontation which started during elections, increased and the atmosphere became tense day by day. The utterances of Farooq Abdullah and his anti-centre stance created an air of political uncertainty in the state in 1984 (Verma, 1994, 299).

The congress party challenged the election results from the day these were declared. They started campaign of vilification against the CM Farooq Abdullah and his government. The essence of the charge was that the government was encouraging anti-national and secessionist force in the state.

The seventh assembly was dissolved on 07 November, 1986 and fresh elections were ordered on March 23, 1987. The Muslim united front and Jamat-i-islami both fundamentalist in the valley and BJP particularly in Hindu dominated belt of Jammu region were the greatest challenge to the NC (F) and Congress (I) alliance.

The data reveals that NC won 41 followed by Congress (I) with 27 seats. The BJP won two seats, MUF and independents won four seats each. The other parties drew blank in this election. Election scene was more competitive in Kashmir valley than in Jammu region right from the beginning of the campaign. The elections in Kashmir valley had consolidated the electorates into two polarized camps-secular forces and fundamentalist they seemed to have fragmented the politics of Kashmir region.

The alliance of NC with Congress (I) in 1987 assembly elections and Rajiv-Farooq Accord gave rise to communal parties in J&K. BJP in Jammu and MUF in Kashmir criticized the Alliance as well as the Accord.

Abdul Gani Lone, who throughout his political career competed through democratic institutions, concluded after 1987 elections: "It was this time that motivated the young generation to say, to hell with the democratic process and all that this is about...let's go for the armed struggle. It was the flash-point. The thought was there, the motivation was there, the urge was there, the demand was there, and the opposition was there. The situation became ripe, and the elections provided a flash-point"

(Widmalm, 1997, 1005-1030). This in turn led to insurgency and militancy in the state particularly in Kashmir division.

After a gap of nearly a decade, because of militancy, considerable turbulence and turmoil in the state, caused by the proxy war imposed by the state of Pakistan, the assembly elections were ultimately held in September 1996. The mandate given to NC in 1996 was unprecedented in the electoral history of J&K. For the first time it emerged as the single largest party in all three regions of the state. It secured 43 seats out of 46 seats in Kashmir, 11 seats out of 37 seats of Jammu division and three out of four seats of Ladakh region (Verma, 1994, 280). Congress won seven seats and BJP eight seats. The Janta Dal secured five, BSP four, independents three seats. The Panthers Party, CPI (M) and Congress (T) got one seat each.

The political processes in the state were restored in 1996 but electoral process continued to remain problematic. Due to continued militancy and separatism, the 1996 assembly election could not commence normally. In any case this election became quite controversial due to heavy presence of security forces and allegations of coercive voting (Chowdhary, 2008, 22-25).

In 1999 Peoples Democratic Party (PDP) was formed by late Mufti Sayeed. Its emergence created vibrancy in the main stream politics of Kashmir. The PDP contested Assembly elections of 2002 and tried to win more and more seats in state particularly in Kashmir region.

The overall voting percentage in the 2002 Assembly election was recorded 43.70. The elections were considered free and fair by almost all parties. The newly PDP won 16 seats and made a coalition government with Congress in the state. This ended the two decades rule of NC in the state. As per the power sharing agreement, Mufti Mohammad Sayeed became the Chief Minister for the first three years and Mr. Ghulam Nabi Azad of Congress for the next three coming years (Shah and Meena, 2016, 108-109).

In 2008, the PDP withdrew her support to Ghulam Nabi Azad's Ministry, two months earlier, because of the Amarnath Land Transfer issue. This resulted the resignation of Mr. Azad, before the completion of his three years tenure (Malik, 2010, 383-384). The Land Transfer issue started the mass agitation in the state which is popularly known as Amarnath Agitation.

The state which was under the governor rule since 10 July, 2008 due to the resignation of Mr. Ghulam Nabi Azad, went to polls for the next general elections. The general election was declared by the election commission of India. This election was held in seven phases from 14th November to 24th December, 2008.

The overall poll percentage was recorded as 61.42 in the 2008 Assembly election, which is greater than 2002 Assembly election. NC remained on the top in tally with 28 seats, followed by PDP with 21, INC 17 and BJP with 11 seats. The JKNPP won three seats, CPI(M), JKDPN and PDF secured one seat each. The independents got four seats in the 2008 Assembly election. The NC with the support of Congress formed the government and elected Omer Abdullah as the full term Chief Minister. The government led by Omer Abdullah faced troubles due to increase in civilian killings by security forces and increase in Human Rights violations in the state.

On September 7, 2014 the floods in the state devastated the huge property and caused several deaths. It was considered that these floods also devastate the NC and INC in the state. The assembly

elections were also held after these floods. The four big political parties INC, BP, NC and PDP contested alone in the 2014 assembly elections. The overall turnout was recorded as 65.52 per cent in the 2014 assembly elections. The outcome of 2014 assembly elections comes as PDP secured 28 seats, followed by BJP 25 seats. The NC won 15 seats and INC secured 12 seats. The others won seven seats in this assembly election.

It was very evident from the participation of people in assembly elections that they want to choose their candidate who is able to do best for them. In last three elections percentage of peoples participation increased in every election. People want good living facilities in their lives.

The PDP with the support of BJP forms the government with Mufti Mohammad Sayeed as its Chief Minister. The formation was made on the basis of common minimum programme. The main objective of this alliance was the agreement which would be best for making peace, harmony and confidence building within the state and across the line of control (LOC) for the full development of democracy through inclusive politics (Zaman, 2016:22-24).

The politics in J&K was changed from the dominance of one party to multi party system. It was also changed from the trend of unopposed returns to the competitive electoral politics. The era of coalition politics which started in the state after 2002 assembly elections continued in the state. The separatist politics that seen to be lost their support rejuvenated after 2008 Amarnath land agitation in the state. The situation was very much worsened in the state because of the growing Human Rights Violations. The emergence of BJP in 2014 assembly elections started a new chapter in Jammu and Kashmir politics.

Conclusion:

The politics of Jammu and Kashmir passed through various phases. The aspirations of people that through democratic process the dispute of Jammu and Kashmir were solved were changed. The people now considered that these elections were only for the fulfillment of basic necessities. The democratic process and separatist politics goes parallel in Jammu and Kashmir.

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